

INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENT OF AGRICULTURE IN THE MODERNIZATION OF THE ECONOMY AND ITS CHARACTERISTICS

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Abstract. *This article deals with the creation and development of new technologies, products, equipment, materials and production growth, the volume of innovative products, and the creation and development of economic support mechanisms for innovative activities.*

Keywords: *economy, agriculture, innovation, modernization, society, strategy.*

INTRODUCTION. The development trend of the world economy testifies to the fact that in all spheres and aspects of human society, especially in many regions of the planet under the influence of global climate change, the economic activities of entities that grow agricultural products, as well as provide services to them in various directions, as one of the main factors in ending poverty and hunger organization based on innovations has gained strategic importance, and continuous improvement of this process is becoming a demand of the times.

Innovation is a necessary element of the implementation of the basic laws of social development, a condition for its development and dynamism. The development of organizations in society takes place through the adoption of various innovations affecting all aspects of their activities. According to the analysis of the trends in the development of science and technology in our country and abroad, it is possible to transfer the economy to the innovative path of development only under the conditions of comprehensive reform of the science and technology field, from scientific research to the production of scientific voluminous products and their entry into the world market.

This reform process can be conditionally divided into three main elements:

- organization of scientific research that allows to expand the fields where the country's science is likely to occupy one of the leading positions in the world;
- network innovation system, including creation of innovative infrastructure that ensures effective commercialization of knowledge;
- modernization of industry based on innovation.

The work to organize the development of these elements in a coordinated manner requires the identification of obstacles to the realization of competitive advantages and the selection of suitable means of development. The main principles of innovative infrastructure development are:

- compatibility with the requirements and opportunities of the national economy;
- maximum flexibility, competitiveness and transparency in the international economy.

Research methodology. Systematic approach, abstract-logical thinking, grouping, comparison, factor analysis, selective observation methods were used in the research process.

Analysis and results. It is necessary to create a fully functional innovative infrastructure (technology parks, business incubators, innovative technological centers, technology transfer centers, venture funds, intellectual property exchanges, marketing centers, scientific and technical development centers) as a segment of the national innovation system.

It is necessary to provide for the development and commercialization of competitive scientific and technical products and technologies in terms of technical equipment and personnel, and the creation and support of new entities of the innovative field, which can ensure their implementation in domestic and foreign markets. The implementation of measures for the innovative development of enterprises allows:

- new or improved technologies, products, equipment, materials, etc. ensuring the growth of production of products (goods, services) due to introduction;
- to increase the share of innovative products to 20% of the total volume of products of innovatively active enterprises, that is, to approach European indicators;
- creation of additional jobs in science and technology and production; ITTKI and innovative projects of financing new additional resources to the innovative sector due to the introduction of schemes;
- creation and development of the necessary innovative infrastructure (technological parks, innovative technological centers, small innovative technological enterprises, etc.), economic support mechanisms for innovative activity entities;
- formation of legislation and normative legal frameworks regulating the relations of the participants of innovative activities;
- creation of systems of training and retraining of highly qualified personnel in the innovative field;
- to support innovative activity participants with information and create innovative project management systems;
- creation of an efficient, market-oriented innovation system that ensures the increase of innovative activity of enterprises;
- implementation of rapid structural changes in production based on the introduction of innovations;
- increase the competitiveness of products (goods, services) and the technical level of production;
- creation of conditions for further promotion of industrial and scientific-technical products in domestic and foreign markets;
- maximum use of best practices and advantages of international cooperation and intersectoral cooperation in the field of innovative activity.

An important aspect of the innovative development system is that it creates new opportunities for the growth of the network in a short period of time in the conditions of the deformation of the economy, the management of innovation processes, and the existence of an information vacuum at the level of agricultural enterprises. The role of the state in the formation of this system is incomparable. "Having extensive information about the scientific and technical capabilities and best practices of agricultural producers in production creates conditions for training them in innovative methods of economic management, mastering the rules of innovation, and providing consulting assistance to increase the innovation activity of ASM.

However, it should be recognized that the agricultural sector, due to its sensitivity and dependence on natural and climatic factors, has a number of difficulties in creating and implementing innovations compared to other sectors, and therefore, its development on the basis of innovative modernization requires deep research and experience in specific and appropriate innovative directions. - requires regular improvement of discovery works (ITTKI). In our opinion,

it is appropriate to carry out the process of creating science and technical-technological innovations related to the branches of our country's economy, including agriculture, and the development of innovative activities, not within a narrow framework within our republic, but in harmony with the achievements of innovative activities in these areas of industrially developed foreign countries.

The innovation process in the agricultural sector is a set of activities related to the delivery of qualitatively new products, economic mechanisms, specific organizational, technical or technological ideas, created on the basis of scientific achievements, to direct use in production. The economic growth in the agrarian sector of the republic is mainly due to the production of import-substituting products and the development of entrepreneurship.

However, the development of the innovative process in the areas based on scientific agrarian technology in the network is not at the level of demand. This is adversely affected by the lack of economic, financial, and legal bases for the management of innovative risks in the network, as well as ways to improve the effectiveness of innovations, assessment of innovation risks and risks, innovation potential in the current conditions.

The strategic goal of the innovation policy is to transform scientific ideas and developments into competitive products, to introduce these products into production, as well as to develop regional scientific and innovative potential, to create a favorable innovation environment that ensures maintenance and development.

The development of innovative activities in agriculture is inextricably linked with the formation and development of the entire innovation system. Its main task is to develop socio-economic relations, increase the level and quality of food supply to the population, increase the efficiency of resource use while reducing negative anthropogenic effects on the ecosystem. The following are the important tasks of the innovative policy aimed at the development of agriculture and the improvement of the productivity of farmers and farm subjects in it:

- compliance of production volumes of basic food products with medical consumption standards;
- production of promising products of interregional exchange and export value;
- added of value share and economic effect high has been production of products;
- products produced in small and large enterprises should be in an optimal ratio, complementing each other;
- increasing the efficiency of resource use by reducing anthropogenic impact on the ecosystem.

One of the important forms of organization of innovative activity in ASM is the formation of innovative enterprises, which provide for the introduction of scientific and technical products to the market of innovations, the provision of information and advice, expertise of projects, proposals and orders, the development of experimental production bases, the creation of financial and credit structures for financing. infrastructure development.

Based on the innovative development strategy of ASM, the formation of an economic mechanism should be carried out in the following directions:

- formation of a system of regulatory and legal regulation of innovative activity;
- Targeted and programmatic development of innovative activities at the republican and local levels of ASM;
- development of public-private cooperation.

It is important to emphasize that each of them is independent and goal-oriented, and all of them should complement each other within the framework of public-private cooperation in network investment.

The implementation of the economic mechanism of the innovative development of ASM, the forms and ways of organizing scientific research, the development of business in the field of scientific and technical activity in the ASM and the introduction of agro-innovation in the mutual cooperation of all its participants.

based on state support at all stages. Therefore, innovation is a necessary element of the implementation of the basic laws of the development of society, a condition for its development and dynamism.

The development of enterprises in society takes place through the adoption of various innovations affecting all aspects of their activity. Because we are sure that in the near future, this will become an important factor for the transition of the national economy to an innovative economy based on the ability to quickly implement ideas and inventions into real practice.

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